

IMPROVING THE SOCIAL MARKETING SYSTEM TO INCREASE THE EMPLOYMENT OF GRADUATES WITH DISABILITIES

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Abstract

This article analyzes the issues of ensuring the employment of graduates with disabilities in the labor market. The problems related to discrimination, infrastructural and institutional barriers, as well as employers' lack of willingness to be inclusive are revealed. The study suggests effective mechanisms for involving young people with disabilities in professional integration based on a social marketing approach.

Keywords: young people with disabilities, employment, inclusive labor market, social marketing, rehabilitation, labor integration.

Introduction. Creating equal opportunities for every member of society, including people with disabilities, is an important principle of social justice and sustainable development. In recent years, Uzbekistan has been implementing a number of legislative measures aimed at protecting the rights of people with disabilities and their involvement in the workforce. In particular, article 42 of the Law “On the Rights of Persons with Disabilities” guarantees the equal right to work [1]. However, in practice, the level of participation of this category of the population in the labor market remains low. According to official data, in 2024, the employment rate among people with disabilities was only 8.5% [2], which is four times lower than among the rest of the working-age population. The reasons for this gap are related to deep social, economic and psychological factors.

The relevance of the problem. According to T.A.Mikhailova, graduates with disabilities are the most vulnerable category in the labor market. Lack of work experience, lack of adapted jobs, as well as the presence of stereotypes in society exacerbate the problem [3]. As a result, young people with disabilities are deprived of economic independence and are socially isolated. New Uzbekistan pays special attention to creating conditions for the active participation of all members of society, including people with disabilities, in economic activities. The International Labour Organization (ILO) estimates the economic losses from the exclusion of persons with disabilities from the labor market in the range of 3-7% of GDP [4].

Legal framework and existing mechanisms. The country has the following legal and economic mechanisms to support the employment of people with disabilities:

- tax benefits and subsidies for employers;
- introduction of quota jobs;
- vocational rehabilitation and retraining programs;
- a system of microcredit and compensation;

For example, if an employer creates an adapted workplace for an employee with a disability, he can receive a subsidy in the amount of 40 times the basic calculation index (BRP). In addition, 50% of the salary of

the accepted employee is compensated for 6 months. However, in practice, only about 10% of employers are aware of such opportunities [5].

Disadvantages of the vocational education system. One of the key factors influencing the employment of graduates with disabilities is the level of their professional training. Since 2007, the list of professions recommended for people with disabilities has not been updated, which does not meet modern labor market requirements. As a result, many young people, having the potential to work, get jobs that are not in demand by the economy.

The need for social marketing. To increase the employment of people with disabilities, the social marketing approach is important, aimed at changing public attitudes towards people with disabilities, forming their positive image, stimulating employers and increasing the confidence of young people with disabilities in their abilities.

The main elements of a social marketing strategy include:

- information policy - the formation of a positive view of the labor potential of people with disabilities;
- awareness campaigns - familiarizing employers with the benefits of inclusive employment;
- motivational programs - stimulating the professional growth of youth with disabilities;
- cooperation platforms - creation of mechanisms for interaction between the state, Non-governmental non-profit organizations and the private sector;

Systemic problems. The analysis shows that the following systemic barriers remain when providing employment for young people with disabilities:

- outdated disability assessment system;
- inadequate workplace infrastructure;
- non-fulfillment of quotas by employers;
- psychological and social barriers;
- insufficient development of inclusive educational programs.

In our opinion, in order to eliminate these problems and increase the employment of people with disabilities at the state level, it is necessary to implement the reforms listed in table-1.

Table-1.

Key strategic directions for increasing employment ¹

Direction	Content
Reforming the system	Revision of the disability assessment system based on modern criteria.
Legal protection	Prevention of discrimination, raising public awareness about labor rights.
Modernization of education	Development and implementation of inclusive vocational training programs.
Cooperation with employers	Strengthening control over the implementation of quotas, expanding the promotion of tax benefits.
Infrastructure adaptation	Provision of physical and technical conditions at workplaces.
Development of social marketing	Creating a positive image of people with disabilities, changing public consciousness.

Conclusions and suggestions. Increasing the activity of graduates with disabilities in the labor market is the most important condition for ensuring the social stability of society. The following measures are proposed for this purpose:

- modernization of vocational education - development of adapted and digital educational programs for youth with disabilities;
- implementing a social marketing strategy - presenting disability not as a “problem”, but as an “opportunity for development”;
- stimulating employers by expanding the system of tax benefits, subsidies and bonuses;
- creation of a monitoring mechanism - strengthening control over the implementation of employment quotas;
- changing public consciousness is the active coverage of positive examples of employment of people with disabilities in the media.

As a result, the involvement of graduates with disabilities in the labor market not only contributes to their social integration, but also makes a significant contribution to the development of the country's human capital.

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¹Author's development